

The Use of Fibre Reinforced Composite Materials in Formula 1 Motor Racing

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Abstract

Over recent years Formula 1 motor racing has developed into a spectacular, world wide event. The various teams involved in the sport have invested heavily in high technology in an effort to gain an advantage over their adversaries. As a result of this the cars have become extremely sophisticated in design, construction and operation. Carbon fibre reinforced composites were introduced into Formula 1 in 1980 via the aerospace industry. Their rapid development within the sport has been such that the entire grid is now totally dependent on these materials in the production of their vehicles. This paper discusses the design requirements which necessitate the use of composites in the cars and chronicles their evolution within the sport. The present and future applications of the various materials, both their attributes and short comings, are discussed along with some thoughts on possible technology transfers to other industries, not necessarily automotive.

Introduction

The Formula 1 motor racing series runs from March to November of every year. Each race is watched by a huge television audience estimated over one year to be in excess of four billion viewers worldwide. The interest in Formula 1 can only be matched by the Olympic Games and World Cup Football, events which only take place once every four years. The multinational media platform has created a unique environment in which the physical skill of the drivers and the very best in science and engineering can compete, with the singular aim of being the best in the world. An intense competitive spirit runs through each and every element of a racing team's activities. The key to success is the ability to obtain the optimum solution to the package of driver, engine, tires, aerodynamics, technical innovation and reliability.

The financial investment required to run a successful team, that is to say one capable of being a regular points scorer, is approximately US.\$25 million per annum. A championship contender would be required to find perhaps double that amount with a specialist engine supplier

investing a similar sum. Whilst money is important, success cannot be bought. It is not the team which spends the most which will win the Championship but the one which spends most wisely. The project management of the various constituent factors is thus vital to the team's fortunes. The pace of development within Formula 1 dictates that designs change continually. A totally new mark of car will generally appear only once per season but the modification and revision is continuous.

A significant percentage of the team's budget is spent on research and development. So much so that the sport has, in recent years, become synonymous with high technology science and engineering. Through the media most people are by now familiar with the various aerodynamic aids used by the designers as well as "active" suspension and semiautomatic gearboxes. The use of composite materials, although not hyped to anywhere near the same extent, has probably contributed most to the performance of F1 cars in recent years. The cars are now faster and safer than ever before. Indeed all of the cars which make up the grid are now totally dependent on composites in their construction.

Design Considerations.

In order to understand the design philosophy behind a Formula 1 racing car it is first necessary to appreciate the various subassemblies which make up the structure. The general arrangement of the constituents of single seater racing cars has, to all intents and purposes, remained the same since the early 60s. The central component, which accommodates the driver, fuel cell and front suspension elements, is the chassis. It is a semi monocoque shell structure known in the business as "the tub". In reality the F1 monocoque bears far more resemblance to an aircraft cockpit, both in terms of shape and construction, than anything one would expect to find on a road. The engine is attached to the rear of this unit by four titanium bolts, and the structure is completed by the addition of the gearbox and rear suspension assembly (Figure 1.). The car's primary structure of chassis, engine and gearbox thus approximates to a "box beam" arrangement carrying the internal loads to their reaction points at the four corners. The secondary structures, floor pan, bodywork, wing configurations, cooling assemblies and the myriad of electronic control systems, are arranged around and attached to, the primary structure at various points.

The chassis is of major importance to the operation of the vehicle. A racing car is "set-up" (optimised) for each circuit. Changes are made to the suspension elements (springs, dampers, anti-roll bars etc.) with the aim of modifying its handling. Any change in the components' stiffness, however small, should be manifest in the balance of the car. This will not occur if the structure transmitting the loads is not of adequate stiffness. The handling will suffer and speed around the circuit will be lost. Similarly, the wings are required to generate negative lift or "downforce" to aid the road holding of the car. It is paramount that they be as stiff as possible so that all of the downforce is transmitted to the wheels rather than being absorbed in deformation, which would reduce their efficiency and increase drag.

As is the case in all theatres of engineering, the designers of

racing cars are required to comply with a stringent set of regulations. The rules laid down by the sport's governing body FISA impose constraints on geometry, strength and weight. Limitations are placed on the overall dimensions of the cars and the sizing of the driver envelope within the cockpit. Over the years a number of safety regulations have evolved involving the carrying of fire extinguishers, easily accessible electrical isolators etc., and requiring a minimum level of structural integrity. The latter is ensured by a number of load cases specified for the design of structural elements. Tests must be performed and passed in the presence of an Official prior to the car being certified for Grand Prix usage. The regulation limiting the minimum empty weight of the car to 505kg is of major significance. Constructing a car to the weight limit is a difficult but vital task if the speed of the car is to be maximised.

It has been estimated that a mass of 20kg above the weight limit equates to a loss of 0.5 seconds per lap around a typical circuit. This does not sound a lot, $\frac{1}{2}$ a second in approximately $1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 minutes, but over the course of a race amounts to half a lap, or several grid positions in a qualifying session. The quest for lower weight coupled with frequent modifications to the statutes, which are aimed at regulating the pace of development with the sport, have stimulated the introduction of new technology in both design and construction. The structural components of the car must be stiff, strong enough to satisfy the loading requirements, tolerant of, and resistant to impact, and of minimum weight. The solution to this problem is achieved by optimising the geometry, quality and efficiency of construction and by using the most appropriate materials. The pursuit of maximum structural efficiency has resulted in a progression of different technologies throughout the history of Grand Prix motor racing. Much of the development has mirrored that taking place in the aerospace industry, emphasising their similarity of objectives. Tubular spaceframes and aluminium bodywork were replaced by folded and riveted shell structures and, more recently, adhesively bonded aluminium skinned honeycomb structures. This logical progression finally led to the widespread introduction of fibre reinforced composite materials. The motor racing business is a surprisingly conservative industry such that quite often the development of technology in racing cars has lagged that in the aircraft industry by as much as a couple of years. Having said that, the demands of intense competition, and much shorter lead times, have ensured that, in certain respects, composite technology may be considered more advanced in F1 cars. This is manifest both in the overall percentage employed in the structure and in the diversity of products used.

The development of composites within the sport.

The first documented uses of composite construction in racing cars date back to the late 1920s and early 1930s in the form of wood and steel chassis. Composites in the form we think of them today, that of fibre reinforced polymers first appeared in race cars in the early 1950s. At that time random orientation glass mat and polyester resins became widely available. This material allowed the relatively cheap production of complex compound curvature bodywork which replaced aluminium. The use of GRP panelling continued through to the late 1980s.

The history of the present day all-carbon fibre racing cars dates from 1980. Ron Dennis' "Project 4 Racing Organisation" merged with the ailing "Team McLaren Racing" to form McLaren International. In designing their first car, the team considered the aluminium skinned aluminium honeycomb construction which predominated at that time, to be exploited virtually to the limit of its performance. The designers chose instead to research the carbon reinforced composites which were beginning to proliferate the aerospace industry.

At the time Europe, and the UK in particular, were considered the leaders in fibre reinforced composite technology. Unfortunately McLaren were unable to solicit any manufacturing support for the project. By chance one of the design team had previously been and employee of the Hercules Aerospace Corporation of Salt Lake City in the USA. Hercules took up the challenge facilitating the assembly of the first carbon fibre monocoques. The structure was laid up over a "male" mould or mandrel using UD prepreg material. The mandrel, made of cast and machined aluminium alloy, was disassembled for removal through the cockpit opening following an autoclave cure of the composite. The basic design and manufacturing process remained virtually unchanged for a number of years and was still the basis of chassis construction used at McLaren up until the 1992 season (Figure 2).

Whilst this method provided a means of producing all of the external panels of the chassis in one piece, it placed severe restrictions on the shapes which could be moulded. It has been said that the use of composites was nothing more than inevitable technological progression. In many respects this is true in that the MP4/1 chassis was mostly a composite version of the previous aluminium design (Figure 3). It should be remembered, however, that the introduction of composites in such a heavily loaded component was a brave step especially considering the adverse publicity attracted by the materials following the problems experienced with jet engine components, and a number of failures of experimental carbon fibre parts on race cars. A further benefit from this method of chassis construction was a dramatic reduction in the number of components making up the monocoque. An aluminium structure required up to 50 pieces whereas the carbon fibre design needed only 5 main mouldings in addition to the single piece outer shell. The composite design proved so successful that it was soon emulated by other teams despite the reservations of a number of designers who expressed serious doubt as to the suitability of such low ductility materials in highly dynamically loaded components.

The next major advance in chassis construction occurred in 1983 at one of the "lesser" teams. In 1983 the German ATS team developed a monocoque fabricated inside female composite tooling. The two halves of the structure were made from woven fabric prepreg and joined at the centre line (Figure 4). Female moulding makes far more efficient use of the available aerodynamic envelope since only a minimum of secondary bodywork is needed to cover it. It also provides an opportunity to optimise the geometry and thus improve its efficiency. The BMW powered ATS was never a leading contender but generally considered to be one of the strongest and stiffest chassis on the circuit. This method of manufacture does however necessitate a join in the main shell and a great degree of laminator skill in order to produce a consistent, repeatable component. Developments in aerodynamic shaping and laminating technology at Williams, and a

number of other teams were such that the male moulding technique gradually became obsolete. The last male moulded chassis was the 1991 championship winning McLaren MP4/6 which was replaced by the female moulded MP4/7 for the following season.

During the design of the MP4/1, McLaren used carbon composites wherever they offered advantages in mechanical properties or a reduction in complexity of the design. To this end in addition to the chassis there were structural ducts on either side of the car for the cooling system, the aerodynamic undertray (floor pan) and the various bodywork panels. A carbon/ honeycomb structure was generally employed except for those points in the bodywork which were required to fit very loosely around the chassis and engine. In those regions the honeycomb was replaced with a syntactic foam core to achieve an adequate stiffness.

Contemporary usage of carbon fibre in racing cars

The use of composites in Formula 1 racing has advanced very rapidly since their introduction. Throughout the period the teams have replaced more and more metal components, such as wings etc, with carbon fibre structures. Figure 5 shows an exploded schematic of the composite parts of the 1992 McLaren MP4/7 racing car. The chassis of a contemporary Formula 1 vehicle consists of typically, 75% by weight of carbon fibre reinforced composites with designers striving to increase that proportion. Exploitation of composites has given teams the opportunity to significantly improve the performance of the cars whilst making them safer for their occupants. Crash safety is a very important aspect of race car design. The enormous energy absorbing capabilities of fibre reinforced polymers has greatly reduced the instance of serious injury within the sport. As a result it is now quite commonplace to see drivers walk away unhurt from quite spectacular crashes which just over a decade ago would almost certainly have been fatal.

Over the years a number of innovative and elegant designs have appeared in Formula 1. Figure 6 illustrates this point. It shows the 1992 Williams FW14B with its aerodynamic sculpting typical of a modern F1 car. In addition to the structural materials a number of speciality composites are used such as carbon-carbon brakes and clutches, and ablative heatshields in and around the exhaust ports. Carbon-carbon composite brake discs and pads were first used by Brabham in 1982 with most other teams quickly following suit. Significant weight saving advantages are gained from using carbon-carbon over the sintered metal components it replaced, coupled with higher coefficients of friction. Without the use of carbon-carbon friction elements it simply would not be possible for the cars to attain their present levels of performance. Engine exhaust temperatures can approach 700°C in still air. As a result it is necessary to produce ablative panels to protect the vulnerable components and subassemblies in that area. The heat shields are made from high modulus carbon fibres impregnated with an inhibited phenolic resin and operate in a sacrificial manner.

To give some idea of the scale of composites used at a leading team, over the 1992 season McLaren used close on 5 tonnes of carbon prepreg in both unidirectional and woven styles, in excess of 1000 m² of film

adhesive and 4m^3 of honeycomb. The rate of increase of consumption is currently about 20% per annum.

The proportion of a current Formula 1 car that is manufactured from composites necessitates the allocation of a significant proportion of the team's operating budget. A team capable of challenging for the championship will consist of around 200 employees to cover all aspects of design, construction and running of the cars. One would expect approximately 10% of the work force to be engaged in composite activity. The team will require a minimum of two autoclaves and air-circulating ovens in addition to a clean room and subassembly area. Tooling is produced using low temperature curing prepreg tooling materials formed over epoxy-based, CNC machined patterns. The timescales demanded in Formula 1 are such that heat curing tooling systems are not generally viable.

The structural materials employed are those based on PAN derived fibre reinforcement (both intermediate and high modulus types) in a toughened epoxy matrix. Practically all of the commercially available honeycomb products are used in both hexagonal and "flex-core" geometries. Hexagonal cell honeycomb is utilised in flat or single curvature areas whilst flex-core is essential for the increasing number of regions exhibiting complex double curvature geometry. Lay up of the various components is carried out by hand according to drawings and lamination sequences provided by the design office. The completed laminations are generally vacuum bagged and autoclave cured according to the manufacturers instructions. Once cured the components are built up into the various subassemblies making up the car and are "fitted out" with the required fasteners and brackets etc.

Present trends and future Developments.

The most recent innovation in composites usage was the introduction of composite suspension components by McLaren in the 1992 season. The replacement of metal suspension members with composites offers significant potential savings in weight. Typically, one expects reductions of the order of 50-60%. There is a further advantage in that the weight being saved reduces the unsprung mass of the car which lowers its inertia and improves handling. Figure 7 illustrates a typical front suspension lay-out. The loading regime experienced by components such as wishbones, track rods and push rods was evaluated from data collected from a number of transducers affixed to the car under both race and test conditions. There followed a year long programme of research, development and testing before the first components were judged to be ready for Grand Prix usage. The first items chosen for metal replacement were the track rods as they were the simplest to produce and experienced a simple tension/compression loading regime (Figure 8).

The need for an exhaustive testing programme is self evident in that failure of such components would have catastrophic results. Construction of the track rods required the development of new manufacturing techniques for the carbon tubes, and adhesive technology for attaching the titanium end-fittings. Areas of concern in terms of performance are tolerance to impact damage, environmental degradation of the adhesive bonds and the component's response to dynamic loading. The track rods were used on the MP4/7 for the

entirety of the 1992, season winning 5 GP victories and taking the runner's up position in the championship. The work has evolved such that composite push rods have run successfully on test and wishbones are at an advanced stage of development.

The manufacturing methods used in Formula 1 have been dominated by autoclave moulding techniques. The process is extremely labour intensive and demands a great deal of operator skill. In short, F1 production is extremely inefficient both in terms of man power and materials. Having said that, the life times of designs and production runs are so short that it is difficult to imagine how else the majority of the parts will be built in the foreseeable future. Techniques such as compression moulding, filament winding and resin transfer moulding are far more suited to mass production than the "bespoke" world of Formula 1. One area which does have potential however is three dimensionally woven structures. 3-D weaving and subsequent impregnation methodologies were pioneered by Aerospatiale and Hercules, predominantly for the production of carbon-carbon warheads and rocket motors of nuclear missiles. Development grades of these materials have been produced with an epoxy matrix from which complex components may be CNC machined (Figure 9). The properties of 3-D woven structures are pseudo-isotropic such that all manner of brackets, bell cranks and other artifacts could be produced. Indeed with a high temperature resisting matrix such as a phenolic, it is not inconceivable that a gearbox casing could be manufactured in composite, although this is obviously some way off.

The level of expertise in composites manufacture, materials science and innovation of design throughout the Formula 1 industry is very commendable. Notwithstanding the ability to build structures is far in advance of our detailed understanding of the design. The complexity of geometry increases each year driven by the goal of aerodynamic efficiency. The future of engineering development within the sport depends on the greater application of science. Improved analysis methodologies leading a better understanding of the various elements which make up the structure of the car, and govern its operation, are clearly required. Sophisticated dynamic testing apparatus and a number of quality control procedures, albeit somewhat rudimentary, have been introduced along with finite element computer codes as we strive to redress the balance between the "art" and science of Formula 1.

Technology transfer - Formula 1 as a research tool

The Formula 1 industry has profited significantly from the use of composite materials. Indeed their dominance is such that a team simply could not take part without a composite car. At the same time the use of composite materials within the sport has extended their applications far beyond their aerospace origin. A Formula 1 team is a very useful research organisation. New products can be quickly evaluated and tested providing valuable feedback to the materials supplier to aid development. Hercules in particular have benefited from their close symbiotic relationship with McLaren which has continued for over 12 years.

A degree of criticism has been levelled at Formula 1 recently over the increasing use of costly technology, raising questions as to its relevance to the construction of ordinary road cars. The notion that

many of the new innovations produced by Formula 1 are not directly transferable takes a very short sighted view of the situation. Active suspension, composite structures and anti-lock carbon-carbon brakes, whilst not used on production cars are all very appropriate technologies in the construction of high speed trains which are far more efficient, safer and ecologically friendly than the motor car.

Devoid of the inertia and bureaucracy of large organisations, and driven by intense competition, new technology can be introduced, tested and modified within very short time scales in Formula 1. Companies such as Shell, Elf, Hercules, Renault and Honda have already benefited technically from their close involvement with Formula 1 teams. Publicity literature from these various companies make constant reference to the use of F1 as a "laboratory facility". It is more than likely that this trend will continue to develop into a very important source of funding for the teams involved.

At the present time the only road cars which employ structural fibre composite materials, albeit at a much lower level of sophistication, are the latest breed of 200 mph "super cars" such as those produced by McLaren and Bugatti. The dominant ethos in car design at present is one of "in-built obsolescence". Cars engineered to last between five and ten years and then be replaced. There has been a drive of late to improve the recyclability of the various constituents of a car. Whilst this is a welcome development, recycling itself is wasteful in that it requires a significant input of energy to convert a component to something else. What is required is longevity. The longer service life of an item the more efficient it is both economically and ecologically. Advanced composite materials are not recyclable. There was much propaganda in the 1980s concerning the recycling of composite structures. This coincided with the emergence of thermoplastic matrix materials. The argument was however inherently flawed since the notion of taking material costing in excess of \$200 Kg⁻¹, inputting energy, and converting it to a moulding compound worth only a few dollars per kilo could never be a viable prospect.

It is not inconceivable that a composite chassis car could be designed in which the major structures have an almost indefinite life time. Composite materials would be extremely attractive in such an application since the primary structure of the car would now be very cost effective due to lower fuel costs spread over much longer timescale and reduction in replacement costs. This is not such a radical suggestion. The Morgan sports car company in Malvern, England, produce wooden chassis cars. The owner of a classic vehicle such as this would certainly expect it to last appreciably longer than an "ordinary" car, perhaps replacing running gear and even the engine during the lifetime of the chassis.

In short, Formula 1 has much to offer many other industries in terms of technology transfer, especially in the field of composite materials. The data base on crash safety in particular will be of use to any transportation system. Having said that it will require a much less blinkered view of the technology from the end user for this to happen.

Figure 1: The primary structure of a Formula 1 racing car consists of the chassis/front suspension, the engine and the gearbox/rear suspension.

Figure 2: Construction of a male moulded carbon fibre chassis.

Figure 3: The McLaren MP4/1 chassis.

Figure 4: Female moulded ATS D6 chassis.

- (1) FRONT WING END-PLATES
- (2) FRONT WING MAINPLANE
- (3) FRONT FLAPS
- (4) NOSE BOX
- (5) CHASSIS
- (6) FORWARD FLOOR
- (7) RADIATOR DUCTS
- (8) REAR FLOOR
- (9) AERODYNAMIC TOPBODY
- (10) QUARTER PANELS
- (11) REAR WING SUPPORT PLATES
- (12) REAR WING ENDPLATES
- (13) REAR WINGS, FLAPS AND VANES

Figure 5: Exploded schematic of the composite components of the 1992 MP4/7 race car.

Figure 6: 1992 Williams FW14B (Courtesy of Brian O'Rourke, Williams Grand Prix Engineering Ltd.)

Figure 7: Typical front suspension layout.

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Estoril Test 3rd October 1990
Ayrton Senna MP4-5C/001

V12T08.PRM
Run No : 1

Figure 8: Example of track rod loading data collected at the circuit.

Figure 9: Complex structure CNC machined from 3D composite.